

Counteraction against selected attacks implemented at the 5G access layer

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- ❑ 5G architecture
- ❑ Security architecture of the 5G system
- ❑ Simplified architecture
- ❑ Selected weaknesses
- ❑ Scheme of countering IMSI-catcher attacks
- ❑ Countering attacks targeting the access network

The 5G system architecture consists of a set of terminals, a radio access network, and a core network.

In terms of security, the 5G network architecture in its initial phase of deployment has all the imperfections that the 4G network has.

Jamming
DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service)
Man in the Middle attacks
Eavesdropping
IMSI-catcher attacks

Architecture of the 5G system

5G network is referred as Service Based Architecture (SBA).

AMF (Core Access and Mobility Management Function)
(podstawowa funkcja zarządzania dostępem i mobilnością)
AUSF (Authentication Server Function)
RAN (Radio Access Network)
SMF (Session Management Function)
UPF (User plane Function)
DN (Data Network)

AF (Application Function)
NSSF (Network Slice Selection Function)
NEF (Network Exposure Function)
NRF (NF Repository Function)
PCF (Policy Control Function)
UDM (Unified Data Management)

Security architecture of the 5G system

3GPP TS 33.501 V17.3.0 (2021-09)

This architecture is general. It only identifies domains particularly sensitive to security problems and does not include detailed solutions.

AN – Access Network, SN – Serving Network, ME – Mobile Equipment, HE – Home Environment

(I) Network access security, (II) Network domain security, (III) User domain security, (IV) Application domain security, (V) SBA domain security

The simplified architecture of the 5G system

Universal Integrated Circuit Card (**Sim Card**)

The **user's equipment (UE)**, the **serving network (SN)** performing a specific service, and the **home network (HN)** to which the user is assigned. The SN consists of base stations that are not within range of the user's home network. The main task of the SN is to provide certain roaming services. In the authentication process, the **Security Anchor Function (SEAF)** mediates communication between the user's equipment and his home network.

The simplified architecture of the 5G system

The HN (Home Network) stores subscriber data in the **UDM (Unified Data Management)** database, which corresponds to the data stored in the USIM. These are used by the **AUSF (Authentication Server Function)** and **ARPF (Authentication credential Repository and Processing Function)** functions to perform authentication processes.

- ❑ 3GPP TR 33.846 - Study on authentication enhancements in the 5G System
 - over 20 solutions to improve authentication and weaknesses detected

- ❑ IMSI-catcher (initial phase of deployment)
 - IMSI-catcher attack, which involves intercepting the IMSI user ID (International Mobile Subscriber Identity) during radio transmission.

 - IMSI-catching is a type of attack on user privacy that involves locating and tracking specific users by collecting their long-term identifiers (IMSI).

IMSI Catcher

An attacker can get an IMSI identifier through either a passive or active attack.

A passive attack involves passively eavesdropping on unencrypted network traffic.

An active attack is the Man-in-the-Middle attack, in which a fake base station captures the IMSI of client devices communicating with it.

IMSI Catcher

In 5G networks, solutions have been introduced to improve the protection of IMSI.

The IMSI used until now, which were sometimes secured using the Public Key Infrastructure, have been replaced by encrypted Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI) converted to a hidden/secret Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI). The SUPI identifier is encrypted with an asymmetric algorithm using the operator's public key.

Especially, in the initial phase when we use 5G and 4G access networks IMSI-catcher is possible.

Countering IMSI-catcher attacks is also possible by transmitting an encrypted or secret IMSI ID.

Scheme of possible implementation of countering IMSI-catcher attacks

The IMSI is sent from the UE to the BS secretly in the form of the r_k value determined by k_u key generated in the UE ($r_k = F(k_u, \text{IMSI})$). (XOR)

The **AMF** function generates a k_p key for the BS, which is used to determine the value of $r'_k = F(r_k, k_p)$ sent from the BS to the UE. This is an authentication of the base station to the UE. The UE then sends the IMSI value to the BS again secretly, this time in the form of the $r''_k = F(k_p, \text{IMSI})$ value. This allows the base station to read the IMSI value in a secret form.

Jamming - detection strategies include:

- (1) monitoring signal power levels to detect sudden drops or spikes, which may indicate jamming;
- (2) analyzing radio transmission statistics, such as the number of errors or lost packets, to detect significant changes that may be caused by jamming;
- (3) employing signal encoding techniques or spread spectrum to make it more difficult to jam the useful signal;
- (4) implementing jamming detection algorithms based on machine learning, which may be able to recognize characteristic features of jamming attacks and automatically respond to them.

DoS (Denial of Service) and DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks

- AI (artificial intelligence) or ML (machine learning) algorithms can be used
- Another way to protect against DoS and DDoS attacks is packet filtering.
- Real-time monitoring and anomaly detection
- Statistical methods can be used to analyze network traffic to distinguish normal traffic from traffic caused by attacks (entropy-based anomaly detection)

In general, all strategies related to combating various types of attacks on the access network consist of two processes: attack detection and implementation of preventive or minimizing measures.

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